

Media Research- Research Paper

Is marriage for love? Exploring Western Heterosexual Wedding Media And Contemporary Consumer Culture

Integrity Statement: "I affirm that this assignment was written by me, in accordance with the rules and regulations governing fraud and plagiarism for UvA students."

Student: Giulia Wagner

Student Number: 14239760

Workgroup Name and Number: What is Love? (Baby don't hurt me...): Media and Romantic Love
Group 5

Instructor's Name: Erinne Paisley

Introduction

Influencer weddings on social media platforms like Instagram look increasingly luxurious, showcasing an “abundance of branded goods” (Winch and Webster 2012), as can be observed when scrolling through wedding content. The new component Instagram specifically adds to it is that there are multiple ways to post content, compared to other platforms, as Instagram concentrates on videos, stories, highlights, and picture posts. This array of sharing options makes it the perfect platform to share one's wedding and influence viewers through various channels. The observed phenomenon is specific to the current age of social media, as weddings originally served the practical purpose of ensuring one's social, financial, and legal status until the middle of the 20th century (Coontz 2004). The paper will focus on heterosexual couples, as this couple dynamic is the cultural norm regarding weddings in Western society (Winch and Webster 2012). It is relevant research to human development, as it shows the significant role of social media in contemporary society and the risk of conforming one's wedding and oneself to societal pressures. The extravagant portrayal of Western heterosexual influencer weddings on Instagram shapes societal expectations by idealizing marriage as the pinnacle of love in a relationship, cultivating a mostly capitalist narrative.

The following paper aims to analyze a diverse set of Instagram wedding content, including relevant influencer accounts, featuring posts, reels, and hashtags, related to weddings. They allow for analyzing concepts such as bridal fiction, capitalism, and cruel optimism reflected in modern weddings and preparations. The paper does not criticize, discourage, or generalize the practice of extravagant weddings as people certainly desire to have a memorable day for various reasons. The research investigates whether certain expectations lead people to organize their weddings out of societal pressures and follow a fantasy shaped by Instagram, a phenomenon that reaches beyond individual choice.

Theoretical Framework And Research Methodology

Wedding expenses have increased notably in the last decades, creating heightened pressures on couples to have the ‘perfect wedding’, feeding a more consumer-driven narrative (Halliday 2021). These societal pressures can even lead women to go on ‘wedding diets’ because of the amount of money at stake on the wedding day and to conform to cultural norms (Neighbors and Sobal 2008). Instagram, the platform this research focuses on, promotes these extravagant weddings tied to huge budgets, feeding into concepts of capitalism acted out by the couple and the viewers of the event (Batool, Yasin, and Islam 2021). The platform drives the desire to achieve the perfect bridal look, as image is more important than authenticity (Winch and Webster 2012). There is a disconnect between weddings and their traditional nature of being an economic and political decision (Coontz 2004). They are becoming a performance and the bridal narrative of the ‘perfect bride’ is part of this spectacle (Boden 2001). Through the analysis of a shift in cultural wedding

traditions, the paper will critically zoom in on the commodification in the popular wedding culture as well as the aftermath of extravagant weddings. The following research will counter-argue marriage as the 'happy end' and the idealized bridal narratives on Instagram, using the notion of cruel optimism (Garlen and Sandlin 2017). The stated concepts will be tied to the societal expectations nurtured through the contemporary trends of wedding perfection.

The research will analyze a diverse set of comparable Instagram content, with accounts featuring posts, reels, and highlights with stories related to weddings. The number of views and comments on the posts provide valuable information on the relevance of wedding content, particularly when in comparison to another, while the viewer responses will shed light on how the content is received by users. Several wedding-related hashtags will further prove the interest in the topic amongst users and the desire to share content, making weddings a rather public event. The influencer accounts in the research serve as evidence for notions of social norms, bridal fiction, and consumerism. By combining the quantitative engagement metrics with qualitative impact a comprehensive understanding of the relevance of Instagram wedding content is provided, closely tied to the aforementioned concepts.

Rising Wedding Expenditure And the Role Of Instagram

Substantial increases in average wedding costs in the Western world have been recorded in the last decades, leading to excessive wedding consumption (Halliday 2021). In the United Kingdom, for example, the average amount spent on a wedding has gone "up 3000% since the 1950s", an overall trend in the West (2021). This pressures couples into spending equal amounts of money, as it has become a norm (2021). Modern wedding media is heavily shaped by the current consumer-led culture and influences of public figures (Winch and Webster 2012). Capitalism is the current leading economic system in the Western hemisphere, characterized by individual interests and thus an often excessive consumption lifestyle. The free markets encourage and advertise the consumption of goods, with the premise of them fulfilling one's life. This capitalistic society is mirrored on Instagram.

The account @weddingbliss for example, promotes materialism and consumption, being one of the most popular wedding-themed accounts on Instagram, with 4,1M followers and 10,7K posts. It features various wedding content, from extravagant dress inspirations to big proposals and flamboyant wedding venues. They are valuable examples of modern picture-perfect weddings, sparing no detail and showcasing lavishness, therefore setting the norm. Taking a closer look at the post's comments, the positive resonance is huge. Under a video of a proposal in Paris in front of the illuminated Eiffel Tower with candles, a big red heart of flowers, and big letters saying "MARRY ME" people commented: "This is a dream for every girl out there 🙌" (@[inamazefilms](#)) or "Manifest 🧡" (@[_mehwish_shhhh_](#)). Another reel shows a wedding ring from

Tiffany & Co. It is expensive, judging from its size, the luxury brand, and the diamond. The comments were again predominantly positive saying “Stunning!!! 🥰🥰🥰” (@emmylew77) or “Every woman deserves this!” (@angelabaldwin73). Both cases illustrate how big expensive rings and proposals have become a dream and expectation of many. The more expensive the more value it holds for the couple and their love. The influencer Samira Radmehr openly shared on TikTok that booking the venue for her Lake Como wedding alone cost 20K, for food and beverages, she paid more than 30K. In her “planning“-highlight on Instagram Samira admits the organization for her lavish wedding was stressful and the costs high. She writes that she was “mentally drained“ during the process because there was so much planning (@samiraradmehr). This statement shows how challenging expensive weddings are to organize, illustrated further by the amounts of stories in her highlight, 63 alone in her “planning“-highlight. Samira’s wedding is an example of a picture-perfect ceremony, found throughout Instagram, which will be examined further on in the paper. Picture-perfect in the case of Instagram connotes filtered pictures, showing only happy moments and capturing every moment with the intent to post them later on.

The vast majority of people follow these lavish trends, regardless of their financial situation (Batool, Yasin, and Islam 2021). They often start saving years in advance, sparing no detail as the wedding-related hashtags on Instagram highlight. The modern assumption is, that a perfect wedding can only be achieved through thorough planning and acquiring an abundance of goods, all strictly necessary and advertised in the media (Winch and Webster 2012). The hashtag ‘wedding planner’ for example was used 26 million times. This showcases the effort and work behind planning the day, which is needed for a flamboyant event. The hashtag ‘wedding’, features over 272 million posts. The sheer abundance of posts illustrates the number of people posting their wedding and making it public, as well as the online relevance of weddings. By creating anticipation of the calendar event with pre-wedding build-ups like proposals and bachelorette parties, the current wedding industry heightens the consumption of the wedding, and the relevance of the day itself (Boden 2001). These huge monetary investments can lead to serious financial issues for couples who do not have the same capital means as Instagram Influencers perpetuating this trend. This leads so far in weddings being “ranked 7th amongst the 43rd most traumatic life occasions“ (Batool, Yasin, and Islam 2021). The problem here lies in the fact that Instagram influencers often get sponsored and have a higher budget to spend than the average Instagram wedding content consumer. Capitalistic narratives are woven of perfect and happy weddings equaling necessary heavy financial investments.

Wedding Media And Consumer Engagement

Instagram has become the most important platform for promoting weddings, as people are open to sharing private information with the public, such as their weddings (Batool, Yasin, and Islam 2021). The platform showcases pictures, reels, stories, and hashtags that regenerate popular concepts of lavishness and bridal ideals daily (2021). Users can partake in the events of others

with just one click, making Instagram among the most popular media applications (2021). The research will shift the focus on influencers perpetuating these expensive weddings, as they provide public insight into this trend and as their title states, aim to 'influence' their viewers.

Interviewees of a survey conducted on the influence of Instagram on their wedding decisions showed a clear agreement that the platform played a vital role, inflicting pressure on partaking in extravagant wedding trends (2021). Interviewees further agreed that influencers shaped their decisions significantly, as they would copy their wedding content for their own event (2021). For example, the influencer @samiraradmehr, touched upon earlier, extensively posted pictures and reels around her wedding. She is an American influencer with 139K followers on Instagram and has multiple highlights with hundreds of stories from her wedding and the planning (including “👰💍planning“, “wedding🇮🇹💍“, “my 👰 shower“ and “wedding pt 2“). Samira started posting about the special day a year before, showing wedding preparations, and posting much content afterward as well. She has around 30 posts documenting everything related to her wedding. The first three posts on her profile are pinned, and all from her wedding, immediately signaling the user the importance of the event for her. The wedding took place in Lake Como, which she flew to with all her guests from California. From the beautifully with flowers and golden cutlery decorated reception to her expensive dress, to a cocktail party on boats on the lake -the wedding spared no details as her pictures prove. On average Samira’s posts have 15 to 60 comments, while under her pinned posts the comments were an average of 100, and most of her wedding reels had 20 to 25K more views than her other content. These numbers illustrate the heightened interest in this type of content compared to her other posts. Wedding content seems to hold a certain relevance to her viewers, as the increased level of engagement highlights. This enthusiasm proves the emotional appeal of wedding content to audiences.

The Instagram couple account @andreaandlewis has 1M on Instagram posting purely their relationship. Their profile picture is from their wedding, signaling they are now a married couple. For their entire wedding process, they have multiple highlights as well, called "Wedding Ideas“, “REVEAL“, “WEDDING“ and “DREAM DRESS“. In the last, the couple lets their followers help them in choosing the ‘perfect dress’, through engagement with polls, stickers, and the emoji-slider sticker. The same concept applies to the “Wedding Ideas“-highlight. Followers are directly involved in the process and decision-making, making the wedding a shared event rather than an intimate one. This participation option makes the platform perfect for engaging consumers emotionally in weddings, fostering real-life engagement with weddings.

Social Pressures And The Perfect Bridal Look

Higher costs lead to heightened societal pressure and standards to look perfect on your special day. The hashtag ‘weddingphotography’ features over 63M posts, making it one of the most popular wedding-related hashtags and highlighting the importance of documenting and posting

your wedding for everyone to see. Samira used this hashtag for her posts as well. The hashtags #weddingflorist, #weddingvideo, #weddingjewellery, and #weddingdecor further exemplify important elements in contemporary weddings, having been used multiple thousands of times.

Fearing an imperfect wedding makes couples conform to modern societal expectations (Batool, Yasin, and Islam 2021). With the average wedding cost in the US nowadays being more than \$20,000, pressures increase to look perfect as much money is at stake (Neighbors and Sobal 2008). These standards lead many women to go on a 'wedding diet'. This hashtag, with 173K posts, shows that it is a popular trend. The featured posts illustrate what the 'perfect bridal look' looks like and what the bridal ideal is (Batool, Yasin, and Islam 2021). In preparation for the wedding, the focus of media often lies on the body of the bride (Winch and Webster 2012). Brides feel the pressure to follow a slim and toned look, creating a new social norm tied to Western wedding media imagery (Neighbors and Sobal 2008). These ideals lead to unhealthy weight-loss methods such as eating less, taking diet pills, or excessively exercising before the wedding, which can lead to extreme cases like 'bridorexia' (2008). Concerning is the fact that women often adopt these behaviors despite having a healthy BMI, as they are influenced by Instagram bridal mass media, making them believe they do not fit into the universal bride-to-be (2008). These weight loss-wishes are often exclusively tied to the wedding, and not to prior existing desires (2008). Often, brides-to-be buy a dress a size smaller, to fit into it once the special day arrives (2008). These findings cannot be generalized, nevertheless, it is important to note the consequences of wedding media and unhealthy expectations, as the majority of brides use extreme rather than subtle weight-loss methods.

One can argue that modern social media has turned the wedding into a 'consumer fantasy', highlighting the disconnect of weddings to ethical values and them becoming purely for viewers (Boden 2001). There is a generally changing social and legal role of weddings, as they are no longer strictly tied to a traditional nature (Coontz 2004). Marriage is no longer necessary to secure one's social status or rights (2004) A century ago, weddings marked the 'birth of a couple', which is not true anymore, as couples often already live together before their wedding day and even celebrate it with their children (Boden 2001). Weddings are currently more often than not celebrated independently from religious reasons (2001). Furthermore, the media started emphasizing weddings as performances, constructing, for example, a bridal identity as previously explained, that is part of the spectacle (2001). This development detaches women from their worth, tying them to unrealistic and detrimental standards, which can lead to the real-life dangerous consequences mentioned afore.

Marriage Idealization Through The Lens Of Instagram

The 'Happily Ever After' theme has existed for hundreds of years, promising eternal and unconditional love through marriage, with a secured happy ending. In Disney movies, love is depicted as the true source of happiness, establishing the ideology that only love can lead to a

fulfilled and happy life (Garlen and Sandlin 2017). Disney consumers become attached to these presented fantasies, reliving them and hoping in this impossible image of romantic love (2017). This paper will tie Berlant's critical concept of 'cruel optimism' to this similar bridal fiction presented by influencers. Like Disney, Instagram reaches millions of girls and women daily, teaching consumers unrealistic, problematic marriage ideals.

In Disney, true love equals marriage and promises it is the primary source of happiness, especially for women, which is why they should strive for it (2017). This ideology can be harmful as it ties women's worth and purpose to marriage and teaches that their greatest goal is to find 'the one true love' (2017). Having this destructive idea constitutes cruel optimism- investing hope in something highly unlikely and compromising yourself when doing so (2017). Marrying 'the one' is a popular narrative and consumed norm in Instagram wedding depictions (Winch and Webster 2012). Marriage is depicted as the pinnacle of love in a relationship, the end goal of every true love. Going back to the account of Andrea and Lewis, this idealization of marriage can be seen in the engagement metrics. Their pinned wedding post and their post about Lewis proposing have the most amount of comments with 1700 and 830 on the account, compared to their other posts with 20 to 80 comments, the same phenomenon the posts of influencer Samira present. This shows that audiences love to engage with wedding content, and it interests them the most about a couple, compared to the activity on the other posts. Enthusiastic comments like "I hope I can find a relationship that will make me this happy" (@elise_livingtestimony) and "Y'all remind me of ticket to paradise" (@noncsi_1000), indicate the desire of followers to be happily married too. Further comments like "I've been waiting on y'all's wedding for so long!! It's so stunning!! Love it!! 🥰💕" (@maywhitakerr), show how invested followers are in influencer relationships, especially when it comes to weddings. Weddings are seen as the pinnacle of love, as a high number of users commented using the word "finally", emphasizing they waited for the wedding to happen and the expectation for couples to marry at some point in their relationship, proving true love.

An example of an extravagant wedding proving the marriage idealization wrong is provided by Italy's most famous influencer, Chiara Ferragni, with nearly 30M followers. She has a highlight filled with approximately 100 stories taking the followers with her during the wedding preparations, and wedding. It did not miss any details, as the entirely "Ferragni"-customized plane for her and her guests proves. Nevertheless, five years later she and singer @fedez divorced. Thus, big expenses do not ensure or equal the success of a relationship. Further, statistics prove that one in three marriages nowadays end in divorce (Boden 2001). Both challenge the notion of a lifelong marriage, as advertised in wedding media. It would be harmful to assume Chiara Ferragni's ultimate happiness source is gone without her husband, as she continues posting happy-looking pictures of her with her two children who seem to bring her a lot of joy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis of heterosexual Western influencer wedding content on Instagram offers valuable insights into modern societal wedding norms and ideals. By zooming in on a diverse set of Instagram wedding content, an illustrated consumer culture can be observed that significantly shapes wedding decisions taken by couples, by fostering societal expectations of weddings needing to be extravagant to be successful. The presented research aims to shed light on the extent to which individuals may be influenced by the created pressures and ideals in their personal wedding experience. These pressures can have a have impact on the physical and financial investments of couples in their wedding planning, leading in some cases to dangerous consequences, such as wedding-related weight-loss methods and financial burdens.

The paper does not assume to present a finished research and analysis, but to raise general awareness of the discussed phenomenon. Hereby the paper does not aim to interfere in the personal decisions of people concerning their wedding or to judge the choice of an extravagant wedding. The current trend observed on Instagram and social media cannot generalize the Western hemisphere, nevertheless, it is important to keep it in mind, as well as its inner workings. Further research could delve deeper into concepts of self-branding of Influencers and the commercialization of their life, tying them additionally to our consumerist society. As the wedding industry similar to most industries worldwide is in constant development, it is also interesting to observe what type of trends will emerge in the next few decades. Already, there is a noticeable diversification of the heteronormative western wedding culture discussed in the paper. An assumption can be made, that diversity will continue to grow, shaping the wedding media landscape and societal ideals and ideas further.

Bibliography

Batool, Sumera, Zaeem Yasin, and Mehwish Islam. 2021. "Role of Instagram in Promoting Extravagant Wedding Trends: An Analysis of Social Pressures on the Middle Class." *Journal of Management Practices, Humanities and Social Sciences* 5 (2): 01–09.

Boden, Sharon. 2001. "'Superbrides': Wedding Consumer Culture and the Construction of Bridal Identity." *Sociological Research Online* 6 (1): 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.5153/sro.570>.

Coontz, Stephanie. 2004. "The World Historical Transformation of Marriage." *Journal of Marriage and Family* 66 (4): 974–79.

Garlen, Julie C., and Jennifer A. Sandlin. 2017. "Happily (n)Ever After: The Cruel Optimism of Disney's Romantic Ideal." *Feminist Media Studies* 17 (6): 957–71. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14680777.2017.1338305>.

Halliday, Daniel. 2021. "Positional Consumption and the Wedding Industry." *Social Theory and Practice* 47 (4): 747–64.

Neighbors, Lori A., and Jeffery Sobal. 2008. "Weight and Weddings: Women's Weight Ideals and Weight Management Behaviors for Their Wedding Day." *Appetite* 50 (2): 550–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2007.11.001>.

Winch, Alison, and Anna Webster. 2012. "Here Comes the Brand: Wedding Media and the Management of Transformation." *Continuum* 26 (1): 51–59. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10304312.2012.630143>.

@andreaandlewis, 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/andreaandlewis/>

@andreaandlewis, 2023, https://www.instagram.com/p/CnevbYwuW8g/?img_index=1

@andreaandlewis, 2022, <https://www.instagram.com/stories/highlights/17890872749099658/>

@samiraradmehr, 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/samiraradmehr/>

@samiraradmehr, 2023, <https://www.tiktok.com/@samiraradmehr/video/7213836456425524526>

@samiraradmehr, 2022, <https://www.instagram.com/stories/highlights/18315919135049305/>

@weddingbliss, 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/theweddingbliss/>

@weddingbliss, 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/p/C3z5LI4LHRi/>

@weddingbliss, 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/p/C3sk8kRoQ4X/>

@chiaraferragni, 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/chiaraferragni/>

'#wedding', 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/wedding/>

'#weddingplanner', 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/weddingplanner/>

'#weddingphotography', 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/weddingphotography/>

'#weddingdiet', 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/weddingdiet/>

'#weddingflorist', 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/weddingflorist/>

'#weddingvideo', 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/weddingvideo/>

'#weddingjewellery', 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/weddingjewellery/>

'#weddingdecor', 2024, <https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/weddingdecor/>

Reflection On The First Draft Of The Final Paper

In this reflection, I will outline the adjustments and revisions I made to the first draft of my research paper on extravagant Western contemporary heterosexual wedding content on Instagram.

To begin with, I included a title page with the title, an integrity statement, and my personal information to make the paper look more professional and appealing. Next, I corrected various sentences and their structures in the paper and took out words that seemed unnecessary to enhance the readability. In my introduction, I stated what it means for weddings to have been "practical", by using a newly found academic paper on the development of weddings. While I already had some secondary sources for this matter, I used Coontz's article to specifically point out the original purpose of a marriage was a century ago. I implemented the source in other parts of my research. I elaborated a more comprehensive theoretical framework, adding information on bridal imagery and the influence of Instagram. In my second sub-argument, I tried highlighting the role of Instagram as well. Beneath the theoretical framework, I included a methodology, explaining my analysis approach on the Instagram wedding content, to further improve the understanding of my research.

These changes aim to enhance the clarity and comprehension of my research object and the concepts in discussion with it, ensuring to meet the standards of an academic paper.